

A Collaborative Approach to Building a Hospital-Centered OMOP Data Layer for Clinically Meaningful ML/AI Applications in Sepsis

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Abstract

Swiss hospitals are adopting the OMOP Common Data Model, building on national semantic foundations established by the Swiss Personalised Health Network (SPHN). Yet clinicians and data teams still lack operational guidance to represent complex conditions in ways that preserve clinical meaning and support reproducible artificial intelligence (AI) applications. We present a collaborative, hospital-driven approach to co-designing an OMOP-aligned data layer for sepsis that connects clinical modeling decisions with AI-readiness and lifecycle requirements. Rather than proposing a new standard, the approach integrates existing semantic frameworks, hospital constraints, and AI reproducibility needs through a modified study-a-thon methodology. The work resulted in shared modeling conventions, ETL patterns, and early specifications for AI metadata and prediction integration, documented in a public OSF project and implemented in multi-hospital test beds. The approach provides a reusable, hospital-centered blueprint for building AI-ready OMOP data layers across clinical domains.

Keywords

OMOP Common Data Model, Sepsis, Clinical Data Interoperability, AI Readiness, Study-a-thon

1. Introduction

Sepsis is a complex, rapidly evolving clinical condition characterised by a dysregulated host response to infection leading to life-threatening organ dysfunction [1]. Its detection and management depend on integrating heterogeneous information, including vital signs, laboratory results, clinical assessments, temporal dynamics, and contextual cues such as estimated onset time (t_0). However, sepsis-related context is captured inconsistently across clinicians' documentation, device-generated data, and hospital information systems, limiting the development of generalisable predictive models and hindering their transfer across hospitals, even when clear patient benefit has been demonstrated [2].

The Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP) Common Data Model (CDM) provides an internationally adopted analytical substrate, complemented by the OHDSI Standardized Vocabularies [3] and, in Switzerland, by Swiss Personalised Health Network (SPHN) semantic conventions [4, 5]. However, hospitals still face unresolved questions on operationalising sepsis-related information in OMOP while preserving clinical meaning and supporting AI readiness. Effective AI applications further require explicit end-to-end reproducibility. Existing initiatives such as Model Cards [6] and

SWAT4HCLS 2026: Amsterdam — Semantic Web Applications and Tools for Health Care and Life Sciences, March 23–26, 2026, Amsterdam, the Netherlands. Editor: Dr. Sabine Österle.

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ML-Croissant [7] address parts of this challenge but do not provide implementation-oriented guidance adapted to hospital operations, motivating the collaborative approach presented here.

Substantial groundwork already existed across Swiss institutions, including demonstrated clinical impact of sepsis modeling and prediction at CHUV [8] and the development of an OMOP transformation pipeline with sepsis-related concept modeling at Inselspital (ISB) through the INFRA – Infection Radar project [9]. These efforts established essential building blocks but also highlighted the need for structured, coordinated, multidisciplinary collaboration to harmonize modeling conventions across hospitals and connect them to AI requirements.

2. Methods: Modified Study-a-Thon

We adapted the study-a-thon model [10] to an operationally focused format suited to hospital environments where multi-day study-a-thons are impractical. The objective was to co-design a hospital-centered OMOP data layer that captures sepsis context at the source while supporting reproducible AI workflows.

Expert Preparation. A small group of clinicians, semantic experts, data engineers, and AI specialists prepared reference materials, including sepsis-specific OMOP concept sets, candidate t_0 definitions, ETL and data-quality considerations, and AI lifecycle requirements.

Operational Workshop. A one-day interdisciplinary workshop [11] reviewed and refined the preparation materials and co-designed a catalog of validation experiments covering data modeling, interoperability, ETL pipelines, raw-versus-OMOP data fidelity, and AI metadata integration.

Implementation in Test Beds. The co-designed experiments are implemented within the ACROSS infrastructure at three Swiss hospitals: CHUV, ISB, and University Children’s Hospital Zurich [12].

3. Results

The study-a-thon [11] produced four thematic challenge areas and a prioritized implementation roadmap, with all outcomes and experiment definitions documented in a public OSF project [13].

Operationalising Sepsis in OMOP. Hospitals converged on a preliminary shared sepsis vocabulary covering core variables, score components, temporal anchors, and distinctions between clinician-assessed and computed values. Reproducible ETL patterns with integrated data-quality feedback were established across heterogeneous environments.

Swiss Health Interoperability Network (SHINe). A follow-up project was accepted in the SDSC Call for Collaborative Infrastructure Projects, establishing a pathway for representing Swiss OMOP efforts within the international OMOP community.

Infrastructure and AI Integration. A minimal alignment layer of essential OMOP variables and temporal constructs was defined to support consistent feature spaces for AI applications. Early benchmarks suggest that near-real-time updates may be feasible for selected domains. A versioned OMOP mapping guide for AI projects [14] supports convergence and onboarding across sites.

Reproducibility Across the AI Lifecycle. Initial mappings between OMOP-derived training datasets and ML-Croissant [7] metadata were defined. A Model-Card-based metadata schema [6] was recommended for clinical AI use cases, together with preliminary specifications for storing AI inference results back into OMOP.

4. Conclusion

Clinically meaningful and AI-ready use of OMOP requires structured, collaborative, hospital-centered co-design rather than top-down standardization. The modified study-a-thon approach provides a reproducible method to align semantic modeling, operational constraints, and AI lifecycle requirements [13]. Although grounded in sepsis, the resulting modeling conventions, ETL patterns, and reproducibility mechanisms are applicable beyond a single use case and offer a practical blueprint for transferable clinical AI applications.

Acknowledgments

This work was conducted within the Bits to Breakthroughs programme[11], supported by the Insel Group and the Swiss Data Science Center (SDSC), and continued through the ACROSS project co-funded by the SDSC and its clinical partners (CHUV, Inselspital, University Children's Hospital Zurich) [12].

Declaration on Generative AI

During the preparation of this work, the author(s) used GPT-5 for style, grammar, and spelling checks. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the publication's content.

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